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Genes that distinguish naive and “primed” human embryonic stem cells.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Here we measured whole transcription by next-generation sequencing methods in human embryonic stem cells for description of the naive and primed hESC states through gene product identification.

Citations

1. Nichols, J. and Smith, A., 2009. Naive and primed pluripotent states. Cell stem cell, 4(6), pp.487-492.

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Results

Genes that distinguish naive and “primed” human embryonic stem cells were identified as individual gene products by RNA-sequencing of human embryonic stem cell cultures.

Naive

- Sts
- Tet2
- Nanog**
- Klf4**
- Tbx3**
- CEBPA
- TFCP2L1
- Smarca2
- GAS7
- Rnf125
- Meg3
- Klf5
- Smarca2
- Zfp42
- Jade2
- Zyg11a

1 Primed
2 **Sox11**
3 **TCF7L1**
4 Ror1
5 Zic3
6 ZIC5
7 Zic2
8 Bex1
9 Nlgn4x
10 Nap113
11 Fez1
12 Fos
13 Iglon5
14 Gli2
15 Dlk1
16 Tunar
17 Otx2
18 **Sall2**
19 **Sox21**
20 Hmga2
21 Tp53l11
22 Vim
23 Vangl2
24 Ror1
25 Id3
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